

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 –3593 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/vol1-issue-4-august-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:
www.arseam.com

TRAINING AND RETRAINING INDIAN WORKERS TO ENHANCE TASK PERFORMANCE: A REVIEW

Prof. (Dr.) Surendra Kumar

School of Management, Babu Banarasi Das University, Faizabad Road, Lucknow

Abstract

The human resources are the key element in any organization as they plan, coordinate, organize and harness all other resources towards the achievement of organizational goals. For any organization to increase its productivity level depends on the level of competence of its workforce. Hence, the need for training and retraining of workers to develop their abilities in order to function effectively and efficiently in the organization. Training is an indispensable tool for human and national development and hence a worthwhile investment for greater productivity in the organization. The paper examined the meaning of major concepts like worker, training and retraining, types of training available to workers, objectives and equally highlighted the effects of training and retraining on workers' task performance in the organization.

Key Words: *Training and re-training, India workers and task performance*

Introduction

Human beings are the pivot of work in the productive venture. This explains why organization and nations take good steps to ensure the effectiveness of individual. Human beings provide ideas, innovations, invention and thereby wealth for the benefit of both employers and employees. This cannot be achieved if workers are not properly trained. Hence, training has always been recognized as an important factor that contributes to improved performance of an employee right from the days of Fredrick Taylor of Scientific Management Fame (Maduabum, 1992:183).

Training can be viewed as the acquisition of skills, knowledge and abilities to enable one function effectively in the performance of one's job. Training of workers is very important to the development and growth of any country most especially the organization. Training is meant for increasing the usefulness of the worker at the work place. The need for training workers in any organization is to develop and use their abilities for the achievement of organizational goals and the fulfillment of individual job satisfaction.

The Federal government recognized the importance of training and re-training of workers to the development of the nation, hence, the National Policy on Education (2008) is a demonstration of government's commitment, Section 7, sub section 4 of the policy states that:

“For all classes, different kinds of in-service training, courses and seminars related to their particular occupation will be arranged on a continuing basis so that all workers may attain proficiency in their work”.

As a result, the Indian government has made certain effort in establishing training centres to train skilled manpower to man the various sectors of the economy. The training is aimed at increasing workers efficiency and productivity level of organization and accelerates economic development in general. The paper therefore examined the meaning of a worker, training and re-training, types of training available to workers. Also, objectives of training and effects of training on workers' task performance in the organization.

Meaning of a Worker

A worker is any individual who is engaged in a particular service in anticipation of agreed wages to be paid in return for the services he renders to his employer (Imhabekhai and Oyitso, 2000). This in essence means that a worker is anybody in paid work. The workplace injury management and workmen's Compensation Act of 1923 section 4 defines a worker as follows:

Worker means a person who has entered into or works under a contract of service or training contract with an employer (whether by way of manual labour or clerical or otherwise and whether the contract is expressed or implied and whether the contract is oral or in writing).

Wikipedia (2011) defines a worker as one who works at a particular occupation or activity. For example, an office worker, one who does manual or industrial labour. A worker can also be a person who is employed to do physical or mental work for wages in order to earn a living (<http://www.yourdictionary.com/worker>). This means that the individual is paid for services rendered or labour exerted in doing his job.

Sills (1972) in International Encyclopedia of Social Science, defined workers as those who produce or transform goods or produce services for their own consumption and for others. This implied that a worker can either be employed in an industry or be self employed. In the context of this paper, a worker is any person employed by the government or private organization to produce goods or render services to humanity and at the end; the person is rewarded through the payment of salaries or wages.

Training and Re-training

The term training has been defined in various ways by different authors. Training refers to improving competencies needed today or very soon (Jackson & Schuler, 2003). Training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for performing the job assigned to him. It is a short term process (http://wiki.answers.com/Q/training_&development-meaning-definition-human-resource-management).

The term training refers to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies as a result of vocational or practical skills and knowledge that relates to specific useful competencies (Wikipedia, 2011). Training is any attempt to improve current or future employee's ability to perform through learning (<http://@dictionary.com/worker/3045>). The purpose of training is to achieve a change in behaviour of those trained. Training is also a learning process that involves the acquisition of knowledge, sharpening of skills, concepts, rules or changing of attitudes and behaviour to enhance the performance of employees. It is activity leading to skilled behaviour (<http://training and development;naukrihub.com>).

According to Nwachukwu (1992), training is an organizational effort aimed at helping an employee to acquire basic skills required for the sufficient execution of the functions for which he was hired. Training generates expertise or skill needed to perform a particular job or series of jobs. Also, Obikoya (1996) is of the opinion that training is a systematic process of altering the behaviour, knowledge and motivation of employees in a direction to increase the effectiveness and organizational goal achievement. Training involves a wide range of professional activities for workers which contribute to their enhancement of work. It can be visualized as the acquisition of techniques, skills, knowledge and experiences which enables the individual to make effective contribution to the combined efforts of a team in a productive process.

On the other hand, re-training of workers involves the renewal or updating of worker's skills, knowledge, attitude, work habits and competencies to enable them perform their assigned responsibilities creditably (Imhabekhai, 2000:120). He went further to say that re-training is a function of observed training needs and the amount of changes which have taken place in the techniques of production. Stressing the importance of re-training to employees, Imhabekhai (2000) quoting Harcon (1961) maintains that:

It is expensive to expect a man to pick up the thread as he goes along. Thus, at different levels in various ways, training for management succession is being fulfilled and grudgingly accepted to be vital for the well-being of an enterprise. Training is a means to an end in itself, the end being the prosperity of the enterprise.

Re-training of workers is very vital to the productivity of any organization considering the technological changes taking place in the world of work. This means workers must be trained to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to be able to meet with these changes and perform their assigned roles in the organization towards the achievement of organizational goals.

Type of Training for Indian Workers

The major forms of training for India workers include the following:-

- (i) In-service training made up of:
 - (a) On-the-job and (b) Off-the-job training.
- (ii) Formal training

(i) In-service Training Programmes

These include training programmes specifically organized for workers who are already in employment. In-service training essentially takes two forms namely: on-the-job training and off-the-job training.

(a) On-the-job training :

It takes place at the work place and possibly while at work. According to Egungwu (1992), on-the-job training takes place at work location. Responsible for its implementation is primarily that of the immediate superiors. On-the-job training is given to new employees by their organization irrespective of their previous training and experience. Orientation or induction training is given to these new workers to familiarize them with their new work environment and the operations of the establishment. The aim of every induction course is the enhancement of the psychological integration of new employees to their work environment. Induction or orientation programmes are desirable and inevitable if the employees must render their services creditably. That is why Pigors and Myers (1984) submitted that:

No organization can choose whether or not to train new employees. All new employees regardless of their previous training, education and experience need to be introduced to their new work environment and

to be shown how to perform specific tasks. Specific training occasions arise when employees are transferred or promoted or when jobs changed and new skills must be learnt, perhaps because of changes in technology and automation.

(b) Off-the-job Training:

These take place outside the work environment and are provided by established training institutions. They are necessary when some employees require the acquisition of the type of knowledge, skills and attitudes which are best provided through series of courses carried out of job environment (Egungwu, 1992). Indian workers are provided with opportunities for continuous learning and acquisition of knowledge and skills needed for effective performance of their jobs and increase in productivity. On-the-job training are provided for workers by established institutions like Administrative Staff College of India (ASCOI) at various locations, Indian Institute of Management (IIM), Centre for Management Development (CMD), Industrial Training Institutes (ITI), and host of others.

Off-the-job training is also provided through regular attendance and participation in seminars, conferences and workshops. According to Imhabekhai, (2000:122), these modes of training connote the gathering of like-minded person for the purpose of education or getting educated about something or a phenomenon through the acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes. Conferences, seminars and workshop are very vital in training manpower in India. This is because they constitute flora for experts, researchers, practitioners, policy makers to come together to share new ideas in the areas and most recent innovations in administration and management of these various establishment.

(ii) Formal Training:

This is the training received in formal institutions such that span from primary to tertiary institutions. According to Ndiomu (1992), formal schools are the traditional places for acquiring knowledge and skills, for they provide the atmosphere for structured learning which makes assimilation process easier. This is so because of the concentration of teaching efforts, aid and feedback mechanism. He went further to say that training in formal schools has the following advantages:

- (i) The performance level of the study can be readily assessed through testing;
- (ii) Ideas and concepts can be standardized;
- (iii) It affords students from various background and experience a forum for interaction; and
- (iv) Resources are put together in one place for maximum utilization.

This type of training provided to a worker depends on the training need of the worker and objectives of the organization. In other words, an organization provides training to its employees on the area he needs training and to achieve organizational objectives.

Objectives of Training Workers

The objectives of training according to Akinwale (2000) can be examined along the following dimensions namely:

- (i) Organizational level;
- (ii) Individual level; and
- (iii) Employee level.

At the organizational level, training is very important in order to meet corporate goals. The need for training must be identified continually in order to achieve organizational goal. Opportunities for training therefore is used as a response to organizational expansion and change. In line with the above, Lane & Robison, (1995) are of the opinion that training impart positively, effectively for optimum performance to achieve corporate goals of the organization.

At the individual level, every organization recruits the best staff it is capable of recruiting within the limits of its environment. Training reduces the work of the manager in terms of close supervision. Training allows for job understanding and competence of the individual. Training at the employee level improves the drive, initiative and quality of work of employees. The employee therefore becomes capable of coping with challenges. Training provides the means of maintaining their own competition by improving knowledge, skills and abilities (Lane & Robison, 1995). The objectives of manpower training and development according to Archive (2008) is to:

- Help yield operational results that will bring about meaningful changes in the output of the organization,
- Develop, sharpen and thus change the employees' attitude as well as increasing their knowledge and skills.
- Changes in techniques and automation and the consequent effect they have on the existing skills and jobs have necessitated the need for the continuous training of the employees.

The primary objectives of workers are to equip workers with the necessary knowledge and skills at all levels for the successful attainment of the desired goal of the organization. To be able to achieve this objective is for the organization to design training programme for its staff. Effective training to an employee will assist in providing the knowledge and appreciation of techniques necessary to enable the trainee to do his job.

According to Oladubu (1991) the objectives of training a worker is:

- To be better equipped to adjust to the changes in the nature of his work.
- To widen the trainee's understanding of the society in which he lives and develop him as a confident person,
- To afford the staff the opportunity of changing their schedules of duties and to be able to perform equally well on them.

Equally, Omole (1999:18) noted that the purpose of industrial training include the improvement of the present or future competence of the individual with a view to improving the competence of the team, group or organization, thereby serving a dual purpose. He went further to say that the rapid changes taking place in the field of technology all over the world demand that workers must be trained to catch up with the changes. Hence, Smith (1977) opines that:

the rate of technological changes has accelerated so that worker can start at the age of sixteen and remain in the same type of job until he retires. Indeed, it could be argued that we have moved into the two or three skill society, where it is the accepted pattern to have to change their type of employment.

The overall aim of training and retraining workers is to improve the efficiency of the work force and to increase the productivity of the organization.

Effect of Training on Indian Workers

The various training programmes undertaken by workers have great impact on the performance of their jobs and the overall productivity of the organization. That is why Ubeku (1975) noted that:

Investment on training and development of staff are wise investment. There are many organizations or establishment in this country due to either ignorance or selfish motives regard training as an expensive venture or waste and so avoid them like plague. What such organizations are interested in are the returns.

Systematic training has contributed significantly to the achievement of organizational goals, provided good judgment is exercised about diminishing returns. Staff training exposes workers to take additional duties and assume position of importance in establishment hierarchy. Technology is becoming more and more complex and even computerization is applied, training and re-training has helped workers to acquire different type of skills and competence required to fully achieve organization goal.

According to Ubeku (1975) the benefits of training and development of manpower to both the organization and individual workers are many. To the organization the benefits include:

- Better production
- Reduce waste accidents and cost of operation
- A stable workforce and
- A better service to customers and clients.

To the individual, the benefits are:

- Job security
- Help with work related problem
- Better pay
- Job satisfaction
- Prospect of advancement and
- Opportunity of realizing potentials

This may be the reasons why Ajileye (1992) opines that training and development is seen as expression of management's desire to assist workers to attain the apogee of self fulfillment. Ndiomu (1992) quoting Appleby says training:

- Improves efficiency and morale;
- Introduction for succession enabling qualified replacement to be available;
- Raises standard of personnel;

- Develops supervisors and decrease the amount of supervision needed;
- And leads to a reduction in scrap rate and improves machine utilization.

In addition, the findings of Collins (2008) on the effect of on-the-job training on Intercontinental bank workers revealed that training brings greater confidence on workers, enriches employee's knowledge and increased performance skill, creates greater efficiency and effectiveness, increases productivity and leads to higher profitability. The study further revealed that there exists a direct relationship between manpower training and productivity of Bank workers. Training improves the productivity of employees and that of the organization and increases profitability arising from staff efficiency.

- Quick and efficient service to customers;
- Eliminating waste through competitive job performance;
- Low labour turnover;
- Rapid expansion of the organization;
- Increase in the network of the organization human capital; and
- Gain government recognition as a responsible corporate citizens.

According to Nickels (2009) the effects of training on employee's performance can often encourage growth within the worker and the organization itself. Training can lead to self-fulfilling prophecy of enhanced output by employee, employee development equals decrease operational costs, leads to greater loyalty to the organization and as well enhanced job satisfaction. He further said that the effects of training on employee performance include meeting and exceeding expectations, cross training of staff, preparing employees for promotion, maintaining a safe environment and reduction of errors.

In addition, the findings of the study carried out by Grips and Savermann (2010) revealed that training of agents had significant effects on the productivity of workers in the organization. In the same vein, Laplagne and Bensted (1999) are of the opinion that

labour productivity growth appears to be enhanced by the joint introduction of training and innovation. This is due to the fact that training requires the support of innovation to benefit labour productivity growth. Zymelman (1976), Myers and Pigors (1981) have also listed a number of benefits to be gained by training employees. According to them, orientation and induction training programme for instance provide new employees the general information that they need about the organization's policies, procedures, practices and rules that will affect them and also about the jobs, they are to perform as obtained in accurate and comprehensive job description. Training provided to workers help the organization to function at an optimum level of productivity which is a direct effort of all employees.

Training brings about change in behaviour with terminal objectives to achieve the goals of the organization through optimal use of manpower. In line with the above, Mitchell (1978) said training can be seen as an attempt by organization to change the behaviour of its members through learning process in order to increase efficiency and effectiveness.

Training and re-training help workers to become more confident in themselves and have a sense of belonging and commitment to the achievement of organizational goal. Hence, if workers receive necessary educational and developmental opportunities necessary to perform their work well, they will not only work with dedication but will aspire to achieve excellence on the job (Ajileye, 1992). Training and re-training of both old and new workers in an organization is not only aimed at promoting the ability of workers

concerned but also promote the good image of the organization as well as preparing workers for taking up higher responsibilities when vacancy occurs.

Amuno (1989) is of the opinion that, those organization that invest resources in workers' training stand the chance of gaining a lot. Definitely, the organization stands a better chance of increased productivity in their various enterprises than those who do not invest in the development of their workers. It is also evident that organizations reap much more benefits than the workers themselves.

Therefore, training serves as a motivating force in improving the efficiency and productivity of the workers in India.

Conclusion

The paper has attempted to discuss the meaning of worker, training and re-training, types of training to workers, objectives of training and equally the effect of training on workers' task performance in the organization. For any organization to maintain higher productivity, the organization must engage in training and re-training of its workforce to meet technological changes taking place in the world of work. This is to ensure improved performance on the job and boost the morale of workers in India.

References

1. Achive, B (2008). Effect of training and manpower development on productivity of workers; retrieved from <http://www.adekass.blogspot.com/impact-of-motivation-on-employee.html> on October 6th, 2011
2. Ajileye, J.A. (1992). Staff welfare scheme: A strategy for motivation in A.D Yahaya and C.I. Akinyele (eds); *New Trend in Personnel Management*, ASCON, Badagry- Lagos. P 160.
3. Akinwale, E.J. (2000). Human resources management: An overview in India: Tribune No. 12, 357, Tuesday – June.
4. Amuno, J.O.E. (1989). The effect of training on the on the job performance of graduates of the centre for Management Development in India. Unpublished P.hD Thesis, University of Ibadan.
5. Balachandran, D.S. (1985). *Personnel: The management of people at work*; New York: Macmillan Publishing Company. 5th Edition.
6. Collins, K. (2008). Effect of training and manpower development on productivity of workers; retrieved from <http://www.adekass.blogspot.com/impact-of-motivation-on-employee.html> on October 6th, 2011.
7. Dearden, L, Reed, R & Reenen, J.V (2005). The impact of training on productivity and wages: evidence from British panel data. Retrieved on October 9th 2011 from <http://ideas.respec.org/p/cep/dp067.html>
8. Egungwu, V.N. (1992). Human resources development and utilization in Indian private enterprises in A.D. Yahaya and C.I. Akinyele (eds); *Human Resources Development and Utilization : Policies and Issues*; ASCOI; Badagry, Lagos p 100.
9. Grip, A.D & Saverman, J (2010). The effects of training on own and co-workers productivity: Evidence from a field experiment; retrieved from <http://wharton.upenn.edu/awfe2010conferencepaper/savermann> on October 6th 2011

10. <http://wiki.answers.com/Q/training&development-meaning-definition-human-resource-management>.
11. <Http://training and development:naukrichub.com>
12. <http://.your dictionary.com/workers>. Retrieved on October 5th, 2011
13. Imhabekhai, C.I. (2000). Manpower Training and retraining for effective health care delivery ; *Benin Journal of Education Studies*, (12&13) 1&2.
14. Imhabekhai, C.I. and Oyitso, M.O. (2000). *Theory and practice of Industrial Relations*; Benin, Monose Amalgamates
15. Jackson, V.S & Schuler, B.A (2003). Meaning of training and development; retrieved on October 2nd, 2011 from <http://www.writework.com/essay>
16. Lane, S.T & Robison, K.C (1995). Meaning of training and development; retrieved on October 2nd, 2011 from <http://www.writework.com/essay>
17. Maduabum, C. (1992). Identification of training needs in A.D. Yahaya and C.I. Akinyele (eds); *New trend in Personnel Management*, Badagry, Lagos, 183.
18. Nwachukwu, C.C. (2008). *Management: Theory and Practice*; Onitsha, Africana FEP Publishers Ltd.
19. Omole, M.A.L (1999). *Industrial Education and Human Resources Development*; Ibadan: Alafas India company.
20. Planning Commission of India (2008). National policy on education, India, Ministry of Human resource Development.
21. Wikipedia (2011). Meaning of worker, retrieved on October 2nd, 2011 from <http://www.the free dictionary.com/worker>.
22. Wikipedia (2011). Definition of training; retrieved on October 6th, 2011 from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/training>.